

ooLeda Framework vs Blockchain - Technical Solutions for Automated Business Trust Protocol

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

To determine which of the above technical solutions is preferred to support automated business trust protocol

2. Material and methods

List out the features and drawbacks of blockchain technology through publicly available articles via internet search.

List out the features ooLeda Framework Gang Chen has created

Compare ooLeda Framework with blockchain.

3. Results

Blockchain technology has become a very hot topic in the last a few years, because of its perceived capability to enable data traceability – accurately trace/identify the past transactions, hence, to facilitate automated business trust protocol. It has been regarded by some as the most disruptive invention since the invention of Internet with potential to lead 4th industrial revolution.

ooLeda framework technology also enables data traceability – not only accurately trace/identify the past transactions, but also accurately trace/identify the update history of transactions (data change history tracking).

ooLeda Framework, implemented with big data transaction handling patented technology, is scalable to handle any requests which can reach this system.

4. Conclusions

ooLeda Framework and blockchain are both technical solutions for Automated Business Trust Protocol.

ooLeda Framework has much more advanced features and ready for large industrial scale trials, while blockchain still at its infant research stage.

ooLeda Framework is scalable, while blockchain is not.

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Table 1: The table below lists out the key feature comparison between blockchain and ooLeda Framework:

	Blockchain	ooLeda Framework
Enabling Trust through data traceability?	Yes	Yes
Avoid double spending Scalable?	Yes No	Yes Yes, handle any requests which can reach this system via Internet
Need data mining?	Yes	No
Support digital currency	Yes	Yes. Also support Fiat currencies
Track data history	Yes	Yes
Track data change history	No	Yes
Support retrospective assessment?	No	Yes
Computation intensive?	Yes	No
Performance	~10 min/transaction	Instant response
Decentralised?	Yes	No, Logically Centralised. However, physically it can be either centralised or decentralised
Energy consumption	~4000 units	1 unit
Security	51% attack	Can leverage the best available security solution on market
Accountability	No one accountable	System operator/owner accountable
Legislation Friendly?	No	Yes, enforce currently legislation
Support FinTech	Yes	Yes
Support Smart Contract	Yes	Yes
Support Cashless Society	Yes	Yes

ooLeda Framework is secured by leveraging the latest security technologies on the market, while blockchain is exposed by 51% attack.

ooLeda Framework is centralised, while blockchain is decentralised.

Blockchain (bitcoin) consumes about 4000 times more energy than ooLeda Framework does.

5. Key Words

Data history traceability, Data change history traceability, blockchain

Author biography

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